

Deliverable 4.2

SOCIAL NORMS-FOCUSED COMMUNICATION PRODUCTS

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Glossary of terms and acronyms

Acronym/Term	Description
OFLW	Zero Food Loss & Waste
CA	Consortium Agreement
HoReCa	Hotel, Restaurant, Catering sectors (including institutional catering)
EU	European Union
MOA	Motivation, Opportunity, and Ability factors of behaviour change framework Vittuari et al. 2023
CS	Case Study of CHORIZO project
FLW	Food Loss & Waste
FW	Food Waste
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PA	Practice Abstract (CHORIZO)
NL	Newsletter (CHORIZO)
D#	Deliverable, such as D2.3 represent the Deliverable 2.3
WP	Work Packages (of the CHORIZO project)
T#	Task, such as T4.2 represent the Task 4.2

Executive summary

The CHORIZO Project is a Horizon Europe, EU-funded initiative that aims to better understand how social norms—socially enforced rules and expectations—influence behaviours related to food loss and waste (FLW) across the food supply chain. The project employs six real-life case studies with partners across Europe to support three main goals: analysing the impact of previous food loss and waste (FLW) reduction actions, generating new evidence on how social norms influence food waste behaviours, and validating the project's communication and science education tools.

The project focuses on four key types of social norms—suboptimal food quality, good provider identity, portion size and food affluence, and socio-economic influences—and distinguishes between injunctive norms (what people think they should do) and descriptive norms (what people actually do), with the goal of improving decision-making and stakeholder engagement to achieve zero food waste.

Drawing on insight from the CHORIZO case studies, this deliverable (or CHORIZO Task 4.2) focusing on designing, delivering, and validating sector-specific communication products for consumers, economic actors, and policymakers, tailored to different contexts and gender considerations. The task has developed five distinct communication products, each tailored to a specific sector of the food supply chain and aligned with relevant CHORIZO case studies includes: messages relevant for households, buffet guest in HoReCa, food redistribution organization like food banks, foodservice kitchen or food banks, and retail or food industry. Each product targets specific behavioural change objectives—such as reducing plate waste, encouraging surplus food donations, and clarifying food date labels—to raise awareness and promote food waste reduction.

The task, begin with a review of 90 relevant interventions from a pool of 400, focusing on those that incorporate social norms and key elements of behaviour change—motivation, opportunity, and ability (MOA). The design of these products is grounded in the MOA framework, aiming to enhance motivation and address barriers to behaviour change, while drawing on lessons from past initiatives in terms of content, context, channels, and strategy. Additionally, findings from CHORIZO case studies and input from project partners were used to define user groups, target audiences, and communication objectives, ensuring the products are tailored and effective.

The development process of the communication products starts with the emphasizing the extraction of sector-specific insights, identification of user and target groups, and definition of communication goals. his process was co-created with case study partners through online meetings, information mapping, workshops, and validation surveys, following an iterative approach. beginning with sector analysis and mapping motivations, opportunities, and barriers to food waste reduction. Communication concepts were then tailored to each target group and designed for delivery by relevant user groups. Messages were crafted to be positively framed, context-sensitive, and aligned with social norms, while avoiding provocative tones that could hinder behaviour change. Visual elements were carefully considered to reinforce the message. The final products were validated with both project partners and target audiences to ensure relevance, clarity, and impact.

Key recommendations from the CHORIZO communication product design process emphasize the need to understand sector-specific behaviours and social norms to effectively reduce food waste. Iterative feedback showed that positive messaging, context-specific language, visual elements, and familiar symbols are most effective. Strategically, the products should be adapted to local contexts, delivered through multi-level user engagement, and monitored for long-term impact. Digital formats allow for customization, and local governments are encouraged to use these tools for public engagement, with potential applications through local and community organizations.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project description

The **CHORIZO Project** (“Changing practices and Habits through Open, Responsible, and social Innovation towards ZerO food waste”) is a Horizon Europe, European Union (EU) funded project, which aims to improve the understanding of how **social norms** (rules and expectations that are socially enforced) influence **behaviour related to food loss and waste** (FLW) generation. Behaviour change is a critical aspect of addressing FLW challenges as it is the result of multiple and interconnected behaviours taking place across various contexts and stages of the food supply chain. The knowledge generated by the project will be used to improve the effectiveness of decision-making and the engagement of food chain actors towards zero food waste.

The CHORIZO project employs **six real-life Case Studies (CSs)** (Figure 1) with partners spread across Europe to serve three interlinked purposes:

- i. To provide information and data on the context and impact of previous FLW prevention/reduction actions undertaken by the Case Study members, thus enriching the evidence-based analysis of previous FLW actions;
- ii. To generate new evidence on the interaction between social norms, behaviour and food waste, to feed into the project’s FLW models and innovation products;
- iii. To validate the communication and science education packages developed within the project.

Figure 1 Name of the Case Studies employed in the CHORIZO project

For the purposes of this project, social norms are defined as rules or guidelines for action (behaviour) that individuals perceive as expected by others within the group they aspire to or belong to. Social norms are examples of non-material social facts- ways of acting, thinking, and feeling that exist external to the individual, which exert a coercive influence, thereby guiding behaviour (Bicchieri & Cristina, 2006). Based on this definition, the CHORIZO project employs the following **four types of social norms** that are relevant to contributing to FLW in various sectors:

- **Suboptimal food/undesirable food quality:** due to sensory deviation, e.g. “unusual shape or colour” (Stangherlin et al., 2020).

- **Good provider identity:** the desire to be a good parent, host, or other social role influences behaviour (Graham-Rowe et al., 2014).
- **Portion size & food affluence:** portion size indicates how much is appropriate to eat, without being perceived as an excessive eater (i.e. with low self-control and attractiveness) (Zhao et al. 2019).
- **Associations between FW behaviour and socio-economic status:** influence of socio-economic status (income, education, employment) on food-related behaviour (Middleton et al., 2018).

CHORIZO explores and applies two types of social norms: injunctive and descriptive (Cialdini & Trost, 1998). Injunctive norms refer to individuals’ perceptions of what actions are considered appropriate within a specific context. Descriptive norms, on the other hand, reflect common or prevalent behaviours and are based on individuals’ perceptions of how likely others are to engage in those normative actions.

1.2 Summary of WP4 & T4.2

Building on the findings from the CHORIZO CSs, WP4 aims to fostering changes with four distinct tasks. Therefore, the WP4 of the project focuses on actor-, context- and gender-specific change fostering towards OFLW, with four specific tasks (Figure 2) including: actor-specific guidance, social norm-based communication and science education products, and capacity-building activities.

Figure 2 Overall outline of the CHORIZO WP4

Therefore, the main aim of WP4 is to foster behaviour changes toward reducing FW, with the objectives including:

(1) to apply the behavioural change theory and the mechanisms linking social norms to FLW behaviour revealed in WP3 into concrete change-fostering actions, taking into consideration the motivations, opportunities, and abilities of sectoral food system actors;

(2) to develop and design actor-specific guidance on social norms to foster change;

(3) to deliver more engaging and effective social-norms-focused communication and school science education to prevent/reduce FLW;

(4) to support the uptake of sector-specific guidance of CHORIZO by building the capacity of the target actors.

Task 4.2 (T4.2) focuses on design, delivery, and validation of sector-specific, social norms-based communication products to reduce FW. The communication products are developed based on the output of CHORIZO tasks related to CS analysis (D2.3) and actor-specific guidance (D4.1) and aim to

deliver a minimum of three communication products, addressing consumers, economic actors and local authority policymakers respectively, while considering context and gender differences.

The task (4.2) focuses on four distinct sectors to explore the characteristics of FW, underlining social norms, motivations and barriers to reducing FW. Thereafter, it defines the various communication products and their specific objectives.

1.2.1 Profiling of the sector and relevant social norms

To create effective communication products, it is essential to understand the sector's background and the underlying social norms. Here, we aim to highlight the key factors that drive behaviour change such as motivation, opportunity and barriers, along with the social norms that influence them summarized from various CHORIZO deliverables (ANNEX 6.4 Review of existing CHORIZO Deliverables).

- **Household sector**

The characteristics of FW in the household sector show that socio-economic characteristics (e.g., age, urbanisation level, gender, social group) do not affect the quality of FW (D2.3). The most typical reason for FW is preparing or serving too much food, and potatoes, fruit, bread, meat and fish, eggs, and vegetables are the most commonly wasted food items (D2.3). High perishability or short shelf life –especially in completely or partially unused food- can increase the likelihood of disposal (D2.3).

Social norms such as the "good provider identity" contribute to FW – particularly during guest hosting or in children's meals and lunch packs – driven by the desire to offer enough food and to ensure there is always enough food at home (D2.3). Households can be clustered by food waste levels: the lower FW group consists of elderly couples, students, or retirees with lower incomes, while the higher FW group is more common in high-income urban households.

The primary motivation for reducing FW in the household sector is economics. However, the motivation for discarding food arises from various reasons, including hygiene concerns of the surplus food, and inability to reuse (D2.3). Households are generally not influenced by what others think of them but act according to personal beliefs or family traditions.

Opportunities and barriers in this sector include the need to raise awareness about proper food planning such as making shopping lists, planning up weekly menus, and checking the cupboards and fridge before buying food (D2.3). Major factors contributing to FW includes lack of skills in food planning, purchasing, cooking and managing leftovers or unused food.

- **HoReCa sector**

The characteristics of FW in the HoReCa sector show that surplus food items are most often generated due to overproduction or over-preparation which requires careful attention and handling. Some of the surplus food items results from the inability to reheat or reuse items from foodservice buffets. Consumers tend to fill their plates with a variety of items, often overloading them, and leading to leftovers that cannot be reused.

The main social norms in the HoReCa sector that contribute to food waste include "good provider identity" and "portion size". In a broad sense, cooks have a strong focus on quality when it comes to serving food, but this can sometimes results in unnecessary FW. Taste and appearance of food, food options, and portion sizes are crucial factors for guests. Men tend to prioritise receiving larger portions, while women value seasonal menu changes. Women may be more likely to leave food uneaten when dining in company, compared to men (D2.3). From the HoReCa guest perspective, finishing or leaving a meal on the plate might be influenced by various social norms such as personal

consciousness, social pressure, hunger, larger or small portions, poor food quality, over-plating, and so on (D2.3). Chefs' practices regarding FW reduction are influenced by societal expectations, perception of guests' reactions to leftover food, management, and colleagues (D2.3).

The **primary motivation** for the HoReCa sector to reduce food waste is economic impact and maintaining a good image. Waste disposal and FW collection services can be very costly for their operations, therefore, the economic aspect is also an essential motivator for the managers to minimize FW (D2.3). Chefs' motivations and responses to social norms regarding FW reduction vary, reflecting both personal convictions and external influences, shaped by societal expectations and workplace culture. Price discounts are effective motivators for pre-ordering which can help to reduce waste from production.

The **opportunities and Barriers** existed in the sector are potential to improve knowledge among general public by raising awareness and consciousness as well as enhancing staff skills through different food service training. HoReCa or foodservice businesses regularly has surplus food available for donation, but donating this surplus is perceived as a high-risk activity. Measuring and monitoring food waste is challenging due to the absence of effective mechanisms in the sector. Most FW in restaurants is considered avoidable, and the main causes include over-preparation, overfilled buffets, inappropriate portion sizes, limited practice of consumers taking home leftovers, preparation residues, over-ordering, and overstocking.

- **Food redistribution (Food bank) sector**

The characteristics of FW in the food redistribution sector are defined by the high degree of heterogeneity in donated food, including all sorts of canned, preserved, and frozen products as well as fresh food (fruit, vegetables, bakery, meat, and dairy products). The type of product also influences the reason behind the donations. Fresh foods are donated because of their short shelf-life, while other products are influenced by seasonality (e.g., ice creams and specific holiday sweets and candies). Long-shelf-life products are donated due to minor packaging damage.

The main social norm in the food redistribution sector that contributes to FW is concern over the safety of surplus food. The relevance of social norms arises from companies' perceptions of what the public might think, which influences their actions. Food items that are still good and safe to consume should not be wasted, even if consumers might not purchase them from retail shelves. This paradox sparks discussions on waste, safety, and social responsibility. These unsellable but still consumable items are considered surplus food and are often donated for redistribution, reinforcing the social norm that suboptimal or undesirable food quality is acceptable in this context.

The **primary motivation** of food donors to contribute to the food redistribution sector and reduce FW is the desire to be part of the solution and to maintain a positive public image. Redistribution organizations primary aim to deliver surplus food to those in need, saving the food that would otherwise be wasted and serving individuals who might not otherwise benefit. Therefore, a key motivational factor behind food donation is the opportunity to make a social impact while also addressing environment concerns. The expected impact of food redistribution sector addresses several key areas like: Social (reducing food insecurity and malnutrition, fostering community cohesion, improving dietary diversity and promoting the well-being of vulnerable group in the society); environmental (reducing the amount of energy, water, time and other resources used to produce food by preventing waste); and economic (preventing financial losses and contributing to the responsible use of resources within the food system).

The **opportunities and barriers** in the sector include the availability of surplus food for donation but also resistance to donation due to its perception as a high-risk activity. Food donors are often reluctant to donate surplus food due to unjustified fears of potential legal consequences. Food safety

remains a paramount concern, due to a lack of transparency on food safety practices and handling procedures (e.g. storage and transportation) earlier in the supply chain. For donor companies, donating surplus products can offer long-term intangible benefits, such as enhancing the organization's social image and contributing to its Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) objectives. Emerging digital tools (apps, online platforms) and technologies have been paving the way for more efficient and streamlined food redistribution processes by enabling the identification, collection, transportation and distribution of surplus food.

- **Retail sector**

The characteristic of FW in the retail sector by households is that larger portion sizes and bulk offers are generally welcomed by consumers due to their lower cost.

The social norms relating to FW in the retail sector include the loss of organoleptic characteristics (understood as appearance, taste and flavour), which is associated with suboptimal or undesirable food quality. This is the most probable reason why consumers throw away food close to its expiration date, due to concerns about product safety (D2.3). FW behaviour and socio-economic status do not contribute significantly to retail FW, as the more expensive a product is, the less likely it is to be wasted (D2.3).

The primary motivation for the retail sector to reduce FW is financial, whereas households are assumed to have a mix of financial and environmental motivations. Consumers often struggle to interpret food expiry dates and tend to overprepare meals to avoid hunger. About 10% of FW generated annually in the EU is linked to improper date marking, which confuses consumers and leads to premature disposal. The use of 'use by' and 'best before' labels contributes significantly to this confusion. The retail sector increasingly shows commitment to food redistribution as a way to maintain a positive social image. It is evident that initiatives in the sector should focus on broader themes beyond FW alone, and include awareness-raising and norm-shifting activities.

Opportunities and barriers in the sector include the use of apps, platforms and digital tools that connect retailers and consumers to facilitate the redistribution of surplus food (e.g. overstocked, nearing expiry, or visually unattractive items) for human consumption. Potential actions from retail sector include: in-store initiatives, technological applications, monitoring systems, and awareness-raising campaigns that influence purchasing, stocking, shelving, retailing, and redistribution practices. In-store actions to encourage consumer purchases of products with various drawbacks (e.g. suboptimal appearance, nearing expiry, overstocked) are often supported by incentives such as discounts or reduced prices.

1.2.2 Objectives of the communication products

This task has been developing a total of five distinct **communication products**; each focused on different sectors or areas of the supply chain and aligned with the relevant CSs:

- **The communication product for Households - “A Zero-Waste host”**
- **The communication product for HoReCa - “Portion size for buffet guests”**
- **The communication product for Food banks - “Guidance pamphlet for ambassadors”**
- **The communication product for Foodservice or Food banks - “Donation decision tree”**
- **The communication product for the Food industry - “Use-by vs Best-before date labelling”**

Each of above communication products listed above targets specific objectives, which are detailed in Chapter 3 Communication Products

. Collectively, their overarching goals are to raise awareness about reducing FW and to motivate behavioural change, including:

- To raise awareness about minimising FW when hosting guests at home.
- To raise awareness among buffet guests about reducing plate waste.
- To encourage HoReCa business to formalise agreements and initiate food surplus donations.
- To support the donation of surplus food from foodservice kitchens when it cannot be repurposed internally.
- To educate and raise awareness about the differences between "best-before" and "use-by" dates.

With these objectives, a total of **five communication products** have been developed, each targeting a specific group. These products can be used and disseminated by relevant user groups (see Table 1). Additionally, all five communication products have been compiled into a separate compendium intended for use by cities and local authorities through the City Interest Group network, offering guidance on how different communication products can be implemented by cities. This compendium is not included in the current deliverable to avoid duplication of information. However, summarize information are included in the ANNEX **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden. Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** to gives the overview that ow these communication products can be used or disseminate through cities or local government (for instance municipalities).

SECTOR	RELEVANT CS	USER GROUP	TARGET GROUP	COMMUNICATION PRODUCT
HOUSEHOLDS	CS on Households (CS1)	Host	Guest	<i>Zero-Waste Host</i>
HoReCa	CS on Hospitality (CS2) and Foodservice (CS3)	HoReCa staff	Guests in buffet settings	<i>Portion size for Buffet Guests</i>
FOOD REDISTRIBUTION	CS on Food Bank (CS5)	Food bank volunteer or ambassador	Foodservice management	<i>Guidance pamphlet for ambassadors</i>
FOODSERVICE (REDISTRIBUTION)	CS on Food Bank (CS5)	Foodservice management	Kitchen staff in foodservice	<i>Donation decision tree</i>
RETAIL/FOOD INDUSTRY	CS on Date marking and Smart packaging (CS6)	Retail shop or food manufacturers	Households and individual consumers	<i>USE-BY vs BEST-BEFORE date labelling</i>
CITIES	All	City practitioners	All above	<i>Compendium integrating all communication products above (presented as an Annex 6.5 Summary of the 'city compendium')</i>

Table 1 Overview of communication products

The following definitions were applied throughout the task and its processes:

- **Sector:** the area of the food supply chain that the CHORIZO project focused on through its CSs.
- **Target group:** the group expected to be impacted by the message and to exhibit behavioural change.
- **User group:** the group expected to use the communication product and deliver the message to the target group.

- **Communication products:** a combination of the message, including its graphic and design elements.

2 METHODOLOGY AND DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

2.1 Methodology

This section outlines the overall approach to developing communication products (Figure 3), with a focus on high-level strategic thinking.

Figure 3 Methodology employed to design the concept for communication products

2.1.1 Review of the existing literature

A review of past and ongoing initiatives/actions has been conducted, serving as inspiration for the development of new communication products within this task. A total of 90 interventions were shortlisted from a pool of 400 interventions listed by CHORIZO WP1 (D1.2). Focus was placed on exploring the communication and educational components of these interventions, particularly those that incorporate social norms and include at least one of the key elements of behaviour change: Motivation, Opportunity and Ability (MOA). Our approach drew inspiration from existing communication efforts, including: content (design), context (message), channels (delivery methods), and strategic approaches used to reach target audiences.

2.1.2 Theoretical foundation for communication product design

The design of the communication products is grounded in the MOA framework – central to the CHORIZO project – which emphasises how communication can enhance the motivation of the target group while accounting for underlying social norms (van Geffen et al. 2016). Additionally, factors related to opportunity and ability (i.e. barriers) are considered to understand how communication can be effectively used as a tool for behaviour change.

2.1.3 Review of findings from the CSs and underline Social Norms

To develop the targeted communication products, the CHORIZO CSs were used to define both the user group and the target group, and therefore the communication objectives. Findings from the CHORIZO CSs research and its associated deliverable (D2.3) served as key sources of information. Furthermore, partners involved in the CSs contributed through co-creation, providing essential input for the development process, such as defining the main communication goals and corresponding objectives.

2.2 Development Process

This section describes the development process of the communication products, including the extraction of sector-specific insights, selection of target groups, and the establishment of communication goals and objectives. It outlines the co-creation activities carried out with the CS partners, along with the practical and iterative steps taken to shape the communication products.

As shown in *Figure 4*, the design process for the communication products began with an analysis of the sectors targeted by the CHORIZO project. Drawing on background information about FW across sectors, the target and user groups for communication were identified. The motivations, opportunities, and barriers (abilities) for reducing FW within each target group were then examined. Finally, tailored communication concepts were developed for each target group, designed to be delivered by the most relevant user group.

Figure 4 Overall process of communication product design

2.2.1 Tools - Workshop, Survey, User co-creation

A co-creation process with CHORIZO CS partners was undertaken to develop communication products tailored to the partner's (sector's) needs:

- **Online meetings:** To gather input from partners and define the concept, several online meetings (via Teams) were conducted to discuss the strategic direction.
- **Information mapping template:** An Excel-based information mapping template was shared with partners to support the extraction of relevant data for the development of the communication products (see in Annex 6.1 Co-creation tool: Information mapping template). The template was useful for analysing the sectors, defining the user and target groups of the communication, setting communication goals and objectives, and providing input on the communication approach (see process in Figure 4).
- **Face-to-face workshop with project partners:** A workshop was held during the project General Assembly (GA) in Bologna, Italy, on 27th February 2025. Feedback on the first draft of the communication products was collected (see the material in Annex 6.3 Workshop materials).

- **Initial validation with project partners:** An online survey was conducted among project partners to collect feedback on the first draft of the communication products, including comments on the message, design and anticipated impact. Feedback was incorporated and the products were updated accordingly.
- **Validation with target group:** As a final step in the design process, the communication products were shared with the relevant target groups through relevant case study partner's network, to test the validity of the product and its anticipated impact (see the result in ANNEX 6.2 Survey questions and result). Feedback from the target group was incorporated, leading to minor updates to the product.

2.2.2 Selection and Delimitation of User and Target Groups

User and target groups for the communication products were selected based on underlying social norms, and the relevance of specific actors in reducing FW. The user group refers to those who will use the communication product to influence the target group, which consists of individuals whose behaviour the communication aims to impact.

The selection of target and user groups was carried out through a co-creation process with the relevant CS partners. Once these groups were defined, setting the communication goals and objectives was a natural next step.

2.2.3 Selection and Delimitation of Message, Graphic and Design

The messages were designed to raise awareness about sustainability and foster motivation to reduce FW, by considering social norms and the context. Positively framed messages were prioritized to enhance motivation and encourage action. The inclusion of graphics to visually reinforce the message was carefully considered. A key focus of the messaging strategy was to motivate actions that reduce FW by reinforcing positive social norms and, in some cases, sparking interaction to sustain those norms. Findings from CS2 (*Hospitality*) were taken into account, as they indicated that provocative messaging can have the opposite effect and may fail to motivate behavioural change, thereby not contributing to FW reduction (D2.3).

3 COMMUNICATION PRODUCTS

This section presents various **communication products**, along with background information, the communication message and guidance on their potential use across different contexts. The background information for the communication products include:

- **Target group:** individuals or groups anticipated to be influenced by the communication message and motivated to reduce food waste.
- **Context of FW (Social Norms):** underlying social norms and shared expectations that influence behaviours leading to food waste.
- **Keywords:** Relevant concepts that support the development and effectiveness of the communication message and its design.
- **Goal and objectives of communication:** primary purpose of the communication message and how can it be effectively achieved?

The **actual communication message** is developed based on background information and integrates both text and visual elements, allowing it to be delivered through various channels to effectively reach the target audience. The **practical application** of the message reflects our suggested approach for reaching and influencing the intended target audience.

Furthermore, all five communication products have been compiled into a separate compendium intended for used by cities and local authorities across EU. To disseminate to cities and local authorities through City Interest Group network established during the CHORIZO project, a separate compendium is written (City Compendium). **The compendium** provides guidance on how different communication products can be implemented by cities, however, is not include in the current deliverable to avoid duplication.

3.1 Communication Product Relevant for Households - *A Zero-Waste Host*

The background information for the communication products- “A Zero-Waste Host”:

- **Target group:** Households (guests visiting the host’s home)
- **Context of FW (Social Norms):** Good food provider identity
- **Keywords:** Meal planning; Sharing motivation for FW reduction
- **Goal and objectives of the communication:** Addressing social norms related to overproduction of meals and reuse of surplus food.
 - Facilitate better communication between those who prepare and serve food and their guests, in order to tailor portion sizes and reduce waste.
 - Share motivation and knowledge about better utilising leftovers at the table with guests.

The Communication message relevant for the household- “A Zero-Waste Host”:

Figure 5 The communication message targeted at Household sector

Practical application of the communication message- “A Zero-Waste Host”:

The communication message *A Zero-Waste Host* (Figure 5) is recommended to be delivered to the target group through wearable items such as aprons or T-shirts worn while cooking (Figure 6). This approach ensures visibility to guests and may spark conversations around actions to reduce FW.

Figure 6 “A Zero-Waste Host” message applied in practice

3.2 Communication Product Relevant for HoReCa - *Portion size on Buffet Guests*

The background information for the communication products- “*Portion size on Buffet Guests*”:

- **Target group:** Guests in buffet setting
- **Context of FW (Social Norms):** Plate or Portion size; Perception of sustainable behaviour.
- **Keywords:** Multiple trips; plate-size adjustment, reduced portion size, group guests
- **Goal and objectives of the Communication:** To reduce plate waste among buffet guests.
 - Encourage guests in buffet settings to take only what they can realistically consume (also discourage excessive food collection within groups).
 - Promote multiple trips to the buffet instead of bringing to much food to the table at once.
 - Support conscious decision-making regarding appropriate portion sizes.

The Communication message relevant for the HoReCa- *“Portion size on Buffet Guests”*:

Figure 7 The communication message targeted at HoReCa Sector

Practical application of the communication message - *“Portion size on Buffet Guests”*:

The communication message *Portion size on Buffet Guest* (Figure 7) is recommended to be delivered to the target group via visual aids in the buffet area, such as TV screens or notice stands (Figure 8). This approach ensures visibility to guests and may help raise awareness about reducing FW.

Figure 8 “Portion size on Buffet Guest” message applied in practice

3.3 Communication Product Relevant for Food Bank - *Guidance pamphlet for ambassadors*

The background information for the communication products- *“Guidance pamphlet for ambassadors”*:

- **Target group:** HoReCa managers, to be approached by Food Bank Ambassadors
- **Context of FW (Social Norms):** Food safety of donated food items; Public recognition and social responsibility
- **Keywords:** Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Social impact, Goodwill and Branding; "Champion"; "Two-sided -handshake", Recognition

- **Goal and objectives of the Communication:** To motivate management (leaders) to formalize an agreement and initiate food surplus donations to the food bank.
 - Highlight the opportunity to enhance the organization's branding and visibility.
 - Instil pride in being part of a socially responsible cause.
 - Provide a clear overview of the donation process and its benefits.

The Communication message relevant for the Food Bank- “Guidance pamphlet for ambassadors”:

The message (Figure 9) provides guidance for food bank ambassadors to help them pitch food surplus donation opportunities to potential donors, particularly within the HoReCa sector. The underlying intention is to provide brief points that can be used to initiate conversation with foodservice managers.

NOTE: This material has been prepared for the CHORIZO partner “Hungarian Food Bank Association” as an user of the material, however it can also serve as a template for other food redistribution organizations to redesign their own materials.

The message can be downloaded with this link:
<https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/Pamphlet-relevant-for-Foodbank->

Figure 9 The communication message targeted at Food-redistribution Sector

Practical application of the communication message - “Guidance pamphlet for ambassadors”:

The communication message *Guidance pamphlet for ambassador* (Figure 9) is recommended to be delivered to target group by food redistribution organizations such as food banks. The guidance document serves as a concise and informative tool (Figure 10) to support ambassadors when pitching to foodservice managers. It outlines key activities, the impact of food redistribution, and provides an overview of the donation process.

The document (message) can be used as a material to distribute during the public event like a “Pamphlet” (Figure 10).

Figure 10 “Guidance pamphlet for ambassador” message applied in practice

3.4 Communication Product Relevant for Foodservice kitchens or Food Banks - Donation decision tree

The background information for the communication products- “Donation decision tree”:

- **Target group:** Kitchen staff/Chefs in the HoReCa sector
- **Context of FW (Social Norms):** Concerns around the food safety of donated food
- **Keywords:** Social and environmental impact, Food safety measures
- **Goal and objectives of the Communication:** To encourage operational staff to donate surplus food when it cannot be repurpose within the business.
 - Reassure staff about the food safety standards for donated food.
 - Provide clear guidance on the proper handover process for surplus food.
 - Raise awareness about the potential for reusing surplus food responsibly.

The Communication message relevant for the foodservice kitchen- “Donation decision tree”:

Figure 11 the communication message targeted at foodservice Sector

Practical application of the communication message- “Donation decision tree”:

The communication message *Donation decision tree* (Figure 11) is recommended to be displayed in foodservice areas, such as kitchen walls (Figure 12). This approach ensures visibility for kitchen staff and serves as a daily reminder to consider donation as a responsible option for surplus food.

The message (decision-tree) can be hanged in the kitchen wall, so it is visible to the kitchen staff (Figure 12).

Figure 12 “Donation decision tree” message applied in practice

3.5 Communication Product Relevant for Retail Food Sector – “USE-BY vs BEST-BEFORE date labelling”

The background information for the communication products- “USE-BY vs BEST-BEFORE date labelling”:

- **Target group:** Retail shop visitors
- **Context of FW (Social Norms):** Confusing between “Best-Before” and “Use-By” date markings
- **Keywords:** Date-marking scheme; Food Quality; food expiration dates, SMART packaging.
- **Goal and objectives of the Communication:** To educate and raise awareness about the differences between "best-before" and "use-by" dates in order to reduce unnecessary FW.
 - Promote understanding of the distinction between "best-before" and "use-by".
 - Encourage consumers to check and properly assess food with “use-by” date.

The Communication message relevant for the food retail sector-- “USE-BY vs BEST-BEFORE date labelling”:

The message (Figure 13) explains the different types of date marking (labelling) that may cause confusion for consumers. The underlying intention is to raise awareness about the distinction between “Use-By” and “Best-Before” dates and emphasis the possible use of products that are close to their “Best-Before” date.

The message can be downloaded via the following link: <https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/Message-for-Retail-Consumer-DateMarking.png>

Figure 13 The communication message targeted at Retail Sector

Practical application of the communication message – “USE-BY vs BEST-BEFORE date labelling”

The communication message *USE-BY vs BEST-BEFORE date labelling* (Figure 13) is recommended to be displayed in relevant areas of retail shops (Figure 14). This approach ensures visibility to customer and helps raise awareness about different types of date labelling. It also encourages shoppers to check products that are close to—or just past—the 'Best-Before' date and to use them if they are still safe and of good quality.

The message (poster) can be displayed in the supermarket area where product with “BEST-BEFORE” date are placed (Figure 14).

Figure 14 “USE-BY vs BEST-BEFORE date labelling” message applied in practice

4 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Key learnings from the design process

The design of the communication products began with a deep understanding of **sector-specific behaviours and social norms**, which are essential for driving behaviour change. This included analysing **Motivation, Opportunity/Barriers** and **Abilities/Skills**. Each sector exhibits unique characteristics of FW, shaped by its own social norms and the motivations of key actors.

Based on this sector-specific insight, a tailored **communication strategy** was developed. It defined:

- The relevant **target group**/audience
- Potential **user groups**
- Clear communication goals and objectives

Special attention was given when setting the objectives, focusing on how to effectively **motivate the target group** to take meaningful action towards reducing FW.

The implementation of social norms-based communication products within the CHORIZO project showcased a **collaborative and creative co-design process**. Co-creation, as the overarching methodology, provided valuable first-hand insights into the needs and behaviours of the target groups, enhancing the usability and relevance of the products.

The development process involved **multiple iterations**, guided by feedback from project partners and potential users of the product. Key learnings from this validation process include:

- Message should be **positive** to trigger action.
- Use of context-specific vocabulary and symbols is effective.
- Graphics are preferred over text-heavy content.
- Familiar elements such as “I already know” text and recognisable icons are recommended.
- Communication can not only shift existing social norms but also establish new ones.

4.2 Strategic recommendations

To maximize the impact and sustainability of the communication products developed under the CHORIZO project, the following strategic **recommendations** are proposed:

- **Contextual implementation:** Finalised products should be adapted to reflect the specific social norms, objectives and even colour schemes of the target user group.
- **Multi-level user engagement:** Messages may need to be delivered through intermediary user groups before reaching the final target audience. In such cases, background information should be shared across all levels to ensure accurate and effective message delivery.
- **Monitor and Evaluate Long-Term Impact:** Establish mechanisms to track behavioural changes over time in order to evaluate effectiveness and support policy advocacy. Data from the CHORIZO project should be leveraged to refine communication content and enable evidence-based decision-making.
- **Leverage digital formats as a template:** As the products are also available in digital format, they can be updated and customised. For example, adding the logo of the implementing organization or adapting content to local contexts is highly recommended.
- **Policy implications:** Local governments can use these communication products as tools for public engagement, facilitating their delivery through relevant organisations such as consumer groups or non-governmental organizations (NGOs). For instance, the household-focused product “A

Zero-Waste Host can be implemented by local organisations with support from municipal authorities.

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6 ANNEXES

6.1 Co-creation tool: Information mapping template

Here are example with "SchoolFood Communication model" for your reference									
User Group: the one who will use the communication product to make an impact on the Target group. School teacher, School-Canteen employee									
Target Group: the one who we like to have impact on with the communication.									
What is the actual goal of the communication, that User group like to have impact on the Target group. Or Why this User group like to Comm									
Profiling of the SECTOR (School Food)		Background on the communication model			Communication product			Remarks	
		User group	Target group	Goal & Objectives of the communication	Profiling of the Target group	Context of the message	Content/Message	Approach/Channel	Remarks
<u>Characteristic of food wasted</u>		Teacher	Pupils	Goal: Objectives: Keywords:	-> -> ->				
<u>Social norms</u>		Parents	Pupils	Goal: Objectives: Keywords:	-> -> ->				
<u>Motivation</u>		Parents	Pupils	Goal: Objectives: Keywords:	-> -> ->				
<u>Opportunity & Barriers</u>		Canteen Staff	Pupils	Goal: Objectives: Keywords:	-> -> ->				
<u>Insight for Communication & learning (D2.3)</u>		Canteen Staff	Pupils	Goal: Objectives: Keywords:	-> -> ->				
		Teacher	Parents	Goal: Objectives: Keywords:	-> -> ->				

Figure 15 Excel template for collecting background information for the communication product

As shown in Figure 15, Excel template were used to map the background information for the communication products in various relevant sector.

6.2 Survey questions and results

Analysis of the responses from the survey for the communication products.

Overview of the survey response

Total of 76 responses have received from 74 Respondents. Participants were requested to choose at least one communication model to response. Furthermore, the project partners were requested to distribute the survey to relevant user group (potential user of the communication model)

Please select the communication messages that you would like to provide feedback.

Figure 16 Distribution of the survey response

Majority of the respondents belonged to consumer and household sector followed to HoReCa sector. The food manufacturing sector were represented in “Other” group response captured with focus group interview by project partner.

Figure 17 Distribution of the respondents' belonging sector

6.2.1 Result on the communication product for Household- “A Zero-Waste host”

Respondents' characteristics

The respondents for the “Zero-Waste host” shared that they tend to prepare more food than needed to ensure there is enough for everyone. Any surplus is saved for later use. They also ask guests about their meal preferences and encourage them to choose their own portion sizes. In contrast, preparing just enough food is generally not considered a preferred approach.

Figure 18 Behavioural characteristics of the respondents on “A Zero-Waste host”

Impact feedback “Behavioural”

Responses regarding intentions to change behaviour indicate that respondents are not inclined to use the apron in its current design, although they acknowledge following the suggestion in the message. Additionally, while respondents express a willingness to encourage others, this is perceived as unlikely to foster new understanding of the issue.

Figure 19 Behavioural change intention of the respondents on “A Zero-Waste host”

Feedback on the concept, design and message

Response on concept and design reflect that the message in the apron could facilitate conversation, however slight improvement on design and visual is needed.

Figure 20 Respondents' feedback on concept and design of “A Zero-Waste host”

Qualitative comments on message and design reflect both positive and negative aspects:

- *Wearing apron in front of guest seems inappropriate*
- *Statements are not actionable, and steps do not hit the mark for individual behaviour change, and steps are contradictory.*
- *Need to be more lighter and funnier which is missing.*
- *Visual is not appealing (more colourful, larger font size and less text, 1 image instead of 4 rules).*
- *Simpler icons- Icons next to the list make the content harder to read and do not contribute to quick understanding.*
- *Layout/design could be more attractive, funnier and catchy!*
- *Not controversial enough to spark some debate.*
- *“Be creative with left overs” is one of the take way message!*
- *“Asking guest preference” in advance and “prepare just enough” seems not to be relevance.*

Factors that influence the decision to use or not use the message reflect some improvement needed in the message ad design:

- *Do not like to wear aprons while preparing food.*
- *Like the idea but not good approach to confront the guest.*
- *The message is too much “in your face”, Blaming, pointing figure, and conveys a sense of moral superiority.*
- *Very preachy, too serious and missing fun factor.*
- *Way to communicate to guests without needing to start a conversation.*
- *Aprons disturb the entertainment part.*

6.2.2 Result on the communication product for HoReCa- “Portion size on buffet guest”

Respondents’ characteristics

The respondents for the “portion size on buffet guest” shared that they encourage guests to make multiple trips to the buffet and support the use of food waste awareness messages displayed around the buffet area. However, advising guests to avoid overfilling their plates or to take smaller portions is not perceived as the most effective approach.

Figure 21 Behavioural characteristics of the respondents on “Portion size on buffet guest”

Impact feedback “Behavioural”

Responses about behaviour change intentions suggest that the message can effectively raise awareness and guide guests toward reducing food waste. Respondents, who also represent potential users of the communication product, expressed their intention to use the message to raise awareness among guests.

Figure 22 Behavioural change intention of the respondents on “Portion size on buffet guest”

Feedback on the concept, design and message

Response on concept and design reflect that the message in the design is clear and easy to understand, that makes the guest feel part of the shared effort to reduce FW.

Figure 23 Respondents’ feedback on concept and design of “Portion size on buffet guest”

Qualitative comments on message and design highlights its usefulness, while also indicating a need for certain modifications with main comments included:

- It could work as it could help to nudge guests.
- Message could be part of a broader story.
- Larger font size to make it visible from distance.
- Could also include concrete facts (with numbers).

Factors that influence the decision to use or not use the message reflect the need of simplification of the design and make it more encouraging:

- Simple implementation and low cost.
- Good impact on the guest experience.
- Ability to communicate a story.
- The messages are positive, encouraging, and not intrusive.

6.2.3 Result on the communication product for Food bank- “Guidance pamphlet for ambassador”

Respondents’ characteristics

Respondents, who are also potential users of the ambassador guidance pamphlet, emphasized the importance of having a document that clearly outlines all key information. This includes core activities, their outcomes, and their societal impact.

Figure 24 Behavioural characteristics of the respondents on “Guidance pamphlet for ambassador”

Impact feedback “Behavioural”

Responses regarding behaviour change intentions suggest that the guidance will be used as a tools by the volunteers/ambassadors.

Figure 25 Behavioural change intention of the respondents on “Guidance pamphlet for ambassador”

Feedback on the concept, design and message

Response on concept and design reflect that the message in the pamphlet is perceived as very clear to understand and explain key activities, outcomes and impacts:

Figure 26 Respondents' feedback on concept and design of “Guidance pamphlet for ambassador”

Qualitative comments on message and design of the pamphlet reflect the usefulness as a tool with key information included:

- Clear and understandable with good summary.
- Colour scheme assign with the food bank's identity.

Factors that influence the decision to use or not use the pamphlet reflect the need of digital version for the convenience of sending by email:

- Useful material to give some information to potential donors.
- The materials are relevant for second stage of the pitch.
- Digital version would be great to send by email as an info-package.

6.2.4 Result on the communication product for foodservice or foodbank- “Donation decision tree”

Respondents' characteristics

Respondents, who are also potential users of the Donation Decision Tree, highlighted their limited understanding of the food donation process, even though all had previously donated surplus food in some capacity.

Figure 27 Behavioural characteristics of the respondents on “Donation decision tree”

Impact feedback “Behavioural”

Responses regarding behaviour change intentions indicate a willingness to follow the food donation guidelines and to encourage others to do the same.

Figure 28 Behavioural change intention of the respondents on “Donation decision tree”

Feedback on the concept, design and message

Response on concept and design reflect that the message in the poster perceive as useful for the target group:

Figure 29 Respondents’ feedback on concept and design of “Donation decision tree”

Qualitative comments on message and design of the poster reflects its usefulness of the design and no updates or changes deemed necessary:

- It able to increase the awareness of food waste to the kitchen staff.
- General steps are covered.

Factors that influence the decision to use or not use the poster perceived as a tool to raise awareness about food waste among kitchen staff with the general steps of the donation process:

- The poster seems to be useful for the kitchen wall and useable.
- Highlights and can help to maintaining the donation process.

6.2.5 Result on the communication product for food industry- "Use-by vs Best-before date labelling"

Respondents' characteristics

The respondents in

Figure 30 Behavioural characteristics of the respondents on "Use-by vs Best-before date labelling"

Impact feedback "Behavioural"

Responses regarding behaviour change intentions suggest

Figure 31 Behavioural change intention of the respondents on "Use-by vs Best-before date labelling"

Feedback on the concept, design and message

Response on concept and design reflect that the message in the design is clear, and distinguish the different between two type of data marking therefore may able to bring the attention of the consumer.

Figure 32 Respondents' feedback on concept and design of "Use-by vs Best-before date labelling"

Qualitative comments on message and design indicates clarity in communication and a perceived potential to raise awareness:

- *The message is clear- "best before" date still can be eaten after that date.*
- *The message may encourages to pay attention to the quality of the food by looking, smelling and not only by considering the date.*
- *Suggestion to add in the tag "Do it at home" with green text.*
- *Choice of colour is good (red.orange.green)*

Factors that influence the decision to use or not use the message reflect the some clarity in the messaging:

- *Positive influence as it increase the awareness of prevention.*
- *"Avoid food waste" and "Look.smell.taste" is not a clear message as it could understood the action be taken as the shop.*

6.3 Workshop materials and feedback (examples)

Group E
Background information and initial thought of communication – Household-Zero-Waste Host

User -> Target group	Goal of the Communication	Social-Norms / Reference Group
Household (Host that invite guest) -> Household (Guest coming over)	Addressing social norms regarding overproduction of meal, and reuse of surplus meal. Keywords: Meal planning; sharing motivation of FW;	Good food provider identity Reference group: Guest

----- Drop your thought, ideas, suggestion on following points -----

Message (Text)- feedback on message/text <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	Graphic / Picture- what kind of graphic or visual can be used with or without text? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
Design with text, graphic & Picture- how can we combine text in the graphic/picture? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	
Channel- How to reach and display to target group <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	Contingencies- what can possibly go wrong? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •

Figure 33 Workshop template to gather feedback on the draft communication product

The workshop conducted with the template (Figure 33) yield the feedback on the draft communication products are summarized as follows:

Message (Text)

- The message “Less is more” is unclear.
- The term “MANUAL” is not clear;
 - Consider changing it to “CHECKLIST,” “BUCKET LIST,” or “RECOMMENDATIONS.”
 - Alternatively, address the guest directly, e.g., “How can you help me avoid our food waste?”
 - The instruction to “Inform about the meal” is unclear and should be refined.

- There is too much text and too many bullet points;
 - Consider using a visual timeline instead.
 - Remove the preparation (“mis-en-place”) section.
- Rephrase the “Serving” section to clarify guest portion sizes or allow guests to decide their portion.
- Adapt phrasing for different outlets or countries, e.g., “Are you very hungry?”

Graphic/Picture

- Use something catchy to show impact—eye-catching visuals, not just text.
- Graphics are not strictly necessary, but text should be engaging.

Design with Text, Graphic & Picture

- Use “ZERO WASTE” (no hyphen).
- Avoid bullet points; consider a timeline format.
- Ensure colour choices are readable and accessible (avoid problematic combinations like brown and green, which can be difficult for those with colour blindness).

Channel

- Create a mock-up (template) that can be printed in various designs.
- Informing guests about the meal at the table is too late; plan communication earlier.
- Make the message visible to guests by moving it to the front or designing aprons with the message on the back.
 - Use two channels, such as aprons and napkins.
- Logic: plan the meal, gather preferences and information, and communicate expectations to guests.
- Consider making aprons from food waste materials and mention this, e.g., “These aprons are made from fabric we used to reduce food waste.”
- Consider moving the message to the front of the apron or redesigning the apron.

Contingencies

- Provide translations in different languages.
- Include “Inspired by CHORIZO” or use CHORIZO colours.

6.4 Review of existing CHORIZO Deliverables

Relevant information for the communication products extracted from various CHORIZO documents such as; Deliverables, Newsletter, Practice Abstract and so on as follows:

Retail	
Retail actors have leverage the possibility of initiating new value proposition centred around food that are probability to being wasted. (D1.4)	D1.4
Previous actions in the retail sector show efforts to raise awareness about date marking for instance; communication campaigns in supermarkets about best before dates and modifying the 'best before' label to read 'also good after, with aim to develop skills or knowledge.	D1.4
It is also evidence from some of the actions that retail sector involve some kind of commitment toward the mechanism around food redistribution.	D1.4
There is evidence from some actions in the retail sector that shows a commitment to mechanisms for surplus food redistribution.	D1.4

About 10% of food waste generated annually in the EU is linked to improper date marking, which often confuses consumers and leads to premature food disposal. The use of 'use by' and 'best before' labels contributes significantly to this confusion.	NL#2
New technologies (e.g. sustainable, and smart packaging) present the opportunity to enhance consumer communication for instance; clear directions and a timeline to preserve product once open. This can help prevent confusion about date marking and potentially extend product shelf life.	NL#2
Household	
Social norms heavily influence wasteful behaviours. Consumers often struggle with interpreting food expiration dates and tend to overprepare meals to prevent hunger (PA#1). As so, there is a need of promoting smarter packaging and challenging the belief of excessive food preparation is desirable that include encouraging meal planning and educating consumers on mindful purchasing, preparation or food storage practices (PA#1).	PA#1
Existing action across household sector are that aimed at gathering data or creating better insight on Food Waste generation or habit, awareness raising and education, practical hands-on tools that focuses to primarily on preventing to waiting food.	D1.4
Primary key success factor to implement the action in the sector identified are to be focused on boarder theme than just Food Waste, activities designed around a specific context to make effect on descriptive social norms, and Involved ambassadors who developed skills regarding how to engage people in the fight against food waste.	D1.4
Digital or mobile apps can keep people engaged for a long periods and hold potential to raising awareness and changing social norms towards less FW.	D1.4
A big opportunity lies in collecting FW data at household levels and link this with habits and food management behaviours.	D1.4
School	
Project-oriented education to young people on the issue of FW with themes around: surplus food, cooking demonstrations from surplus vegetables, sustainability, responsible consumption, and environmental impact from food waste.	D1.4
In school environment, Peer pressure and perceptions of food appearance, texture, and taste contribute to wastage. As so, should prioritize open communication between parents and students and integrate food system awareness into educational activities. Educational tools that facilitate the collaboration among students, teachers and parents as well as canteen staff is key. Pupils can support each other in accepting less visually appealing foods, parents can involve pupils in the lunch-pack preparation, teacher can supervise lunch break, and canteen personnel can promote balance eating habits and provide educational materials,. (PA#1)	PA#1
Points for intervention to General Awareness Raising intervention	
Emphasises the current challenges within the food ecosystem, encompassing concerns like issues of climate change and gastronomical heritage of the regions.	D1.4
Highlight the importance of choosing climate-friendly food and how it connects to less food waste	D1.4
Highlight the importance of relevant UN's global goals for sustainability, such as SDG-12.3	D1.4
Highlight the proper management of food and promote responsible consumption. With the help of informative talks, trainings (including materials) and advice for responsible habits in the management and use of food.	D1.4
Highlight Environment and social consequences by reflecting the current consumption model.	D1.4
Create urgency of addressing food waste as a common challenge with the need for a combined effort.	D1.4
Highlight food waste as a challenge and emphasis the consequences it could bring in relation to economy, environment and health.	D1.4
Encourage active citizenship and spreading the ethical value of food, solidarity and cooperation to encourage the culture of conscious consumption.	D1.4

Table 2 Summary of the finding from the CHORIZO documents

6.5 Summary of the “City Compendium”

The “*Social Norms-based communication materials to reduce food waste-A compendium*” (City Compendium) serves as a key guidance document for cities, outlining how they can effectively utilize the CHORIZO communication products. Since much of the content overlaps with this document (deliverable), only the essential and non-redundant information will be highlighted here.

FW waste is a widespread issue throughout the food chain, including in urban areas, where local governments can play a key role in encouraging people to change how they buy, consume, and value food. Effective communication is a powerful tool for cities to influence daily habits and shift social norms. A set of tailored communication resources—developed with CHORIZO case study partners—targets specific urban contexts like schools, households, supermarkets, and restaurants, using evidence-based messages that resonate with people's values. These resources were designed through a structured process that analysed food waste across sectors, identified target and user groups, and explored motivations and barriers to reducing waste, resulting in adaptable tools for local governments to promote a culture of wasting less.

Figure 34 front page and Table of Content of the “City Compendium”

Communication products can be adapted and used by local governments and their partners. This compendium contains five communication resources, each with background information, a ready-to-use communication product, and guidance for implementation. The resources are organized by user (city agency) and target group (recipient of the communication message):

1. Department of Education/Sustainability → School cafeterias and pupils

Focus: Raise awareness among pupils and staff about food waste, portion sizes, and the environmental and health impacts of wasted school meals.

2. Department of Sustainability → Retail and supermarkets

Focus: Help shoppers and staff understand food date labeling and normalize the sale of imperfect but edible products.

3. Department of Sustainability → Households

Focus: Support residents with meal planning tips, shopping guidance, and practical ways to reduce spoilage and waste at home.

4. Department of Sustainability → Restaurants, hotel chains, universities

Focus: Encourage portion control and reduce plate waste in buffet settings by promoting conscious consumption habits.

5. Department of Social Services/Commerce → Bakeries, food festivals, food manufacturers

Focus: Promote safe, simple food donation systems and connect businesses with local redistribution organizations.

1. How cities can use communication products relevant for awareness raising among Household

When hosting guests at home, people sometimes feel pressure to arrange for too much food. This is a general feature of being a host so that you don't want guests to feel that there is too little food. With the Zero Waste Host resource hosts can be assisted in planning more realistic portions and reuse leftovers, without sacrificing a generous and welcoming atmosphere.

Cities can use this resource in communications campaigns or at public events, especially around holidays or cultural celebrations. It encourages residents to rethink what it means to be a good host, and to show that care and respect also mean not wasting food.

2. How cities can use communication products relevant for awareness raising in buffet setting

Buffets are an effective way to serve many guests. They are used across multiple contexts in both public and commercial food services. However, buffets are also potential sources of food waste. This communication tool aims to encourage guests to start small, go back for seconds if they're still hungry, and avoid piling up their plates.

Cities can share this message across both public and private food service sectors. Furthermore, public food service contexts, hold significant potential to raise awareness about food waste reduction – whether at public events, university cafeterias, or any publicly managed dining settings like restaurants in public buildings. It helps people make more sustainable choices without feeling restricted, helping food service institutions to reduce waste.

3. How cities can use communication products relevant for food donation partnership pitch

Many restaurants, hotels, and food producers are open to donating surplus food but may be afraid of issues with hygiene or food safety or may not know how to start. This tool helps food banks, redistribution organizations and local officials approach businesses with a clear, compelling message about why donation is doable and impactful, and how they can get involved.

The material highlights the social value of donating, reassures businesses about food safety, and shows how being part of the solution can support their public image. Cities can use this tool as a framework to build new partnerships and strengthen local redistribution networks.

4. How cities can use communication products relevant for surplus food donation decision tree

Kitchen staff and management in hotels, restaurants and cafes often want to reuse or donate surplus food but aren't sure how certain surplus food items should be handled. This decision tree provides practical guidance to help them make choices that can reduce food waste without compromising food safety.

Cities can share this resource through training, events, or hospitality networks. It supports the management, as well as the people on the frontlines of food preparation, to take action and best utilize the surplus food, instead of throwing good food away.

5. How cities can use communication products relevant for awareness raising on date marking

A lot of edible food gets thrown out because there is a widespread lack of knowledge on date labels. This tool explains the difference between "best before" and "use by" dates, helping shoppers make informed choices.

Cities can work with local supermarkets to display the materials in stores, near fridges or dry goods. It can also be used as part of the food waste literacy training in home economics at school.

CHORIZO PROJECT

